

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

MELD SCORE. CAN IT BE USED AS A POSSIBLE PREDICTOR OF EARLY RE-BLEED AFTER ACUTE VARICEAL HEMORRHAGE?

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Abstract:

Introduction: Treatment with vasoactive drugs, prophylactic antibiotics, and endoscopic techniques is the recommended standard of care for patients with acute variceal bleeding. However, treatment failure occurs in about 10–15% of patients. Model for End-stage Liver Disease (MELD) scoring system is used as a tool to assess the severity of the liver disease. It is now being used as a predictor of survival and variceal rebleeding. The study aimed to determine the positive predictive value of MELD score in predicting rebleeding in chronic liver disease patients undergoing intervention for variceal bleeding taking endoscopic findings as a gold standard.

Methods: A total of 100 patients who had undergone intervention for variceal bleeding and were suspected to have a rebleed on MELD score were enrolled in the study. Patients were called for regular follow up after every 2 weeks for 3 months or in case of hematemesis immediately report to the emergency department and to the study department. The presence of bleeding from the same site was included. All the collected data were entered and analyzed into SPSS v25.0. The positive predictive value was calculated and presented as a percentage. Data were stratified for age, gender, history of diabetes, and INR. The Chi-Square test was applied.

Results: A total of 100 predicted to have rebleeding on MELD score in CLD patients who had undergone endoscopic intervention were enrolled in this study. There were 68(68.0%) males and 32(32.0%) were females. The mean age of subjects was 46.3 ± 14.3 years. The overall frequency of outcome as true positive in patients predicted to have a rebleed on MELD score in CLD patients who had undergone endoscopic intervention was 66(66.0%).

Conclusion: MELD score can be used as a possible predictor of early variceal rebleeding. It can identify patients who are at a substantially increased risk of rebleeding over a short term. Patients having a MELD score of more than 20 have a high risk of rebleed.

Keywords: Chronic Liver Disease, MELD Score, Variceal Bleeding, Acute Variceal Hemorrhage, Re-bleed.

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Please cite this article in press Tehreem Fatima et al, *Meld score. Can it be used as a possible predictor of early re-bleed after acute variceal hemorrhage?., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2021; 08(1).*

INTRODUCTION:

Viral hepatitis is a major cause of morbidity and mortality and a rising cause for concern in Asian countries. Hepatitis C induced chronic liver disease (CLD) and cirrhosis are major sources of morbidity and mortality in Pakistan [1]. The liver is involved in the synthesis of plasma proteins involved in hemostasis including pro- and anticoagulant factors, pro- and anti-fibrinolytic factors, and thrombopoietin [2].

In patients with advanced liver diseases complex alterations in the hemostatic system arise which are related to decreasing hepatic synthesis or a consumptive coagulopathy which leads to coagulopathy and ultimately bleeding. Portal hypertension due to liver cirrhosis causes gastroesophageal varices and bleeding from them which continues to be one of the most feared and deadly complications of cirrhosis and portal hypertension [3, 4]. In some patients, there is a risk of Variceal rebleed as well. Variceal rebleeding is described as clinically significant bleeding that occurs ≥ 120 hours after the first hemorrhage, provided that hemostasis was initially achieved [5].

Several tools have been used to assess the chance of rebleed. Few studies have used MELD score with PPV for this purpose which can serve as useful medical decision-making tools for guiding patient care. The MELD score uses values for serum creatinine, serum bilirubin, and the international normalized ratio (INR) for prothrombin time to predict three-month survival. Positive predictive value varies with the prevalence of the disease and there is a lack of local published data on this topic. Hence, there is need to determine the positive predictive value of MELD score in Pakistan as predicting rebleeding in chronic liver disease patients undergoing intervention for variceal bleeding taking endoscopic findings as gold standards. This will help in keeping such patients under close observation and regular follow up which can help us in early detection and taking proper steps in the patients which can help in reducing the mortality associated with the rebleeding in these patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted at Gastroenterology Department, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi from November 7th, 2019 to May 6th, 2020. This is a Cross-Sectional Study. A sample size of 100 cases was calculated with a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error and taking expected PPV of MELD score in predicting rebleeding among the CLD patients who had undergone endoscopic intervention to be

77%.⁷ Sampling Technique used was Non-Probability Consecutive Sampling.

Patients having MLED (appendix-I) of ≥ 20 at the time of presentation with an episode of hematemesis were predicted to have rebleeding after endoscopic intervention on MELD score. Patients who had undergone endoscopic intervention (banding or injection sclerotherapy) having sudden severe epigastric pain with ≥ 1 episode of haematemesis (with three months of endoscopic intervention) underwent endoscopy and direct visualization of the bleeding from the last site on intervention was labeled to have rebleeding after the intervention.

Positive Predictive Value was calculated by this formula:

$$PPV = \frac{\text{True positive}}{\text{True positive} + \text{False positive}} \times 100$$

True Positive were patients suspected to have rebleeding after endoscopic intervention on MELD score later found to be true on endoscopy. False Positive were patients suspected to have rebleeding after endoscopic intervention on MELD score later found to be false on endoscopy.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients of both genders with ages in the range of 18-70 years predicted to have rebleeding on MELD score in CLD patients who had undergone endoscopic intervention as per operational definition
- Patients who signed written informed consent to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients who are taking antiplatelet therapy like aspirin warfarin
- Patients with systolic blood pressure < 90 mmHg after resuscitation.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:

After approval from the ethical review committee of the hospital, 100 patients who had undergone intervention for variceal bleeding and suspected to have to rebleed on MELD score present in the Emergency Department of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi and who fulfilled the above criteria were counseled and explained the details of the study. Written informed consent and detailed history were taken from each patient.

These patients were discharged once the discharge criteria were met. They were called for regular follow-up after every two weeks for three months or in case of hematemesis immediately report to the emergency department and to the study department.

After resuscitation again the endoscopy of these patients was performed and the presence of bleeding from the same site or different site (cross-checked with the clinical records of the previous endoscopy) was done.

All the data were noted and recorded into the proforma along with demographic details of the patient. All the endoscopies and endoscopic interventions were done by the same consultant to eliminate and confounding variables were controlled by exclusion.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE:

All the collected data were entered and analyzed into SPSS v25.0. Numerical variables i.e. age, history of diabetes, and INR were presented by Mean \pm S.D. Categorical variables i.e. gender and PPV were presented as frequency and percentage. The positive predictive value was calculated by the following

formula and was presented as a percentage. Data were stratified for age, gender, history of diabetes, and INR. Post-stratification, the Chi-Square test was applied taking a p -value of ≤ 0.05 as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Total 100 predicted to have rebleeding on MELD score in CLD patients who had undergone endoscopic intervention were enrolled in this study. There were 68(68.0%) males and 32(32.0%) were females. The mean age of subjects was 46.3 ± 14.3 years.

There were 15(15.0%) subjects in the 18-30 years age group, while 36(36.0%) and 49(49.0%) were in 31-45 years and >45 years age groups respectively.

According to INR, 65(65.0%) patients had INR <2.5 s and 35(35.0%) had INR >2.5 s. There were 39(39.0%) subjects who had history of diabetes mellitus.

The overall frequency of outcome as true positive in patients predicted to have rebleeding on MELD score in CLD patients who had undergone endoscopic intervention was 66(66.0%).

Table 1: Characteristics and demographic data of patients

Parameters	Sub-groups	Percent
Gender	Male	68
	Female	32
Age groups	18-30 years	15
	31-45 years	36
	>45 years	49
INR	<2.5 s	65
	>2.5 s	35
Diabetes mellitus	Yes	39
	No	61

Table 2: Shows PEP data stratified with respect to age, gender and duration of the procedure.

	Sub-groups	True positive	False-positive	Total	p-value
Outcome		66	34	100	
Stratification of outcome with respect to gender	Male	44	24	68	0.690
		64.7%	35.3%	100.0%	
	Female	22	10	32	
		68.8%	31.3%	100.0%	
Stratification of outcome with respect to age	18-30 years	8	7	15	0.136
		53.3%	46.7%	100.0%	
	31-45 years	21	15	36	
		58.3%	41.7%	100.0%	
	>45 years	37	12	49	
		75.5%	24.5%	100.0%	
Stratification of outcome with respect to the history of diabetes mellitus	Yes	29	10	39	0.158
		74.4%	25.6%	100.0%	
	No	37	24	61	
		60.7%	39.3%	100.0%	
Stratification of outcome with respect to INR	<2.5 s	44	21	65	0.626
		67.7%	32.3%	100.0%	
	>2.5 s	22	13	35	
		62.9%	37.1%	100.0%	

DISCUSSION:

The risk of rebleeding is not homogeneous through the overall spectrum of patients with variceal bleeding, suggesting the need to stratify the rebleeding risk and to adjust the intensity of therapy according to this risk [6]. This concept is especially important considering the existence of several therapeutic alternatives (multiple drug therapy, band ligation, transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt, surgery, and liver transplantation) with different risks, applicability, and costs [7].

In the current study, early rebleeding occurred in 66% of the patients and the meantime for rebleeding occurrence was 2.59 ± 1.55 days. There was a significant difference between patients without rebleeding and patients with rebleeding, wherein patients with rebleeding had a younger age, more frequent application of the Sengstaken Blakemore tube, more units of packed RBCs, a larger size of esophageal varices, higher serum creatinine, higher INR, higher serum total bilirubin and a significantly higher MELD score than non-rebleeding patients.

Patients with rebleeding had a higher Child class and mainly had esophageal varices. The rate of rebleeding in this study was very high compared with other studies. This may be attributed to multiple operators with variations of experience and skills who carried out the endoscopic intervention. Other causes may play a role, such as different etiologies of liver disease, Child classification of the patients, and the severity of portal hypertension.

The Altamirano et al. study on 60 consecutive cirrhotic patients with acute variceal bleeding revealed that the early rebleeding rate was 13%, and variables associated with early rebleeding were serum albumin, creatinine and the number of transfused blood units in the first 24 h [8]. In our study, serum albumin was not significantly different between rebleeders and non-rebleeders.

The 5-day failure rate was 13% in the study of D'Amico et al. active bleeding on endoscopy, hematocrit levels, aminotransferase levels, the Child-Pugh class and portal vein thrombosis were significant predictors of 5-day failure [9]. In the study by Abraldes et al. of 117 patients, 18 patients (15%) had a 5-day failure. Multivariate analysis identified three variables independently associated with 5-day failure: hepatic venous pressure gradient of at least 20, systolic blood pressure at the admission of less than 100mmHg, and nonalcoholic cause of cirrhosis [10].

In the study by Hunter and Hamdy [11], 15 of 100 patients rebled or died within 5 days of AVH. Compared with non-rebleeders, these 15 patients had a significantly higher mean MELD score than the other patients. There was active bleeding at the time of endoscopy in 53.3% of them, and white nipple sign was present in 73.3% of them. This study concluded that active bleeding or white nipple sign at the time of endoscopy are predictors of early rebleeding and mortality. These findings do not agree with our study results as neither active bleeding nor signs of recent bleeding were significantly different between rebleeders and non-rebleeders.

We also found that at a cutoff MELD score of more than 20, the sensitivity was 90.91%, specificity 75.64%, PPV 51.3%, and NPV 96.7%. This is comparable to the results by Hunter and Hamdy [11], who showed that the MELD score (>18) was a significant predictor of early rebleeding and mortality after variceal bleeding. However, in our study, the AUROC was much higher than that reported by Altamirano et al., [8] with their MELD AUROC equal to 0.46.

CONCLUSION:

MELD score can be used as a predictor of early variceal rebleed. It can help us identify patients who are at a substantially increased risk of rebleeding over a short term. Patients with a MELD score of more than 20 have a high risk of rebleeding.

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